

Fertilizer management—organic

Effect of farmyard manure application on yield and soil fertility in rice - wheat rotation

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We studied the effect of applying four graded levels of farmyard manure (FYM) (0, 10, 20, and 40 t/ha) on yield and soil fertility in a rice - wheat rotation. FYM was applied in a single dose in Jun 1989 or in four equal splits each June for 4 yr prior to transplanting rice (PR 108) followed by wheat (HD2329). The experiment was laid out in a randomized block design. Soil samples (0-15 cm depth) analyzed before starting the experiment showed that the Typic Ustochrept was sandy loam in texture, had pH of 8.3, and was nonsaline (EC 0.3 dS/m). Inorganic carbon content was low (6050 kg/ha) and bulk density was 1.52 Mg/m³.

Grain yield of both rice and wheat increased significantly with graded levels of FYM. The highest yield (6.7 t/ha) was obtained using 40 t FYM/ha over 4 yr in four equal splits (see table). The

Effect of FYM application on rice and wheat yields.^a

FYM applied ^b (t/ha)	Rice (t/ha)	Wheat (t/ha)
0	4.1	1.4
10*	4.2	1.6
10**	5.9	1.9
20*	4.5	1.9
20**	6.1	2.0
40*	5.0	1.7
40**	6.7	2.5
CD (P = 0.05)	0.7	0.4

^a Av of 4 yr. ^b* = applied in a single dose during Jun 1989. ** = applied in four equal splits to rice each year.

residual effect of lower levels of FYM (10-20 t/ha) on wheat yield was not significant. Average yield of rice and wheat was significantly more when FYM was applied in four equal splits than as a single application. The effect was more pronounced in rice; the residual effect on wheat yield was also conspicuous.

Soil organic carbon content improved with graded levels of FYM application from the initial value of 6050 kg/ha in Jun 1989 to 9600 kg/ha in May 1993 (see figure). Soil organic carbon content was highest where FYM was applied at 40 t/ha. It was significantly higher where

Organic carbon (1000 × kg/ha)

Organic carbon content of soil in May 1993 after 4 yr of experimentation, Ludhiana, India.

split doses of FYM were applied each year than where a single large application of FYM was made.

To maintain soil fertility at higher levels and to obtain higher rice and wheat yields, FYM should be applied to rice each year in splits rather than as a single large dose. ■

Crop management

Relationships between soil properties, crop and pest management practices, pest intensity, and crop performance in rainfed lowland rice

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Holistic field surveys with integrated production level- and crop protection treatments were conducted at four rainfed lowland sites in northeast Thailand and in the Mekong Delta, Vietnam, in 1992. At each site, 4-5 farmers' fields were subdivided into plots receiving either no pest control, pest control according to farmers' practices, or fungicide and insecticide applications 4-5 times during the growing season. Fields were visited repeatedly during the growing season to collect data on crop development, yield, dynamics of disease and pest severities, water conditions, physicochemical soil properties, and crop and pest manage-

ment practices. Descriptive analyses of the data were done.

Improved traditional varieties with superior grain quality prevailed in Thailand, while high-yielding IRRI varieties prevailed in Vietnam. Actual yields, final panicle numbers, and areas under the leaf area index progress curve were generally higher, while growth duration and plant height were shorter in Vietnam than in Thailand (Table 1). The data indicated more favorable physicochemical soil properties and much higher crop and pest management inputs in Vietnam than in Thailand. High incidence of drought was observed during the

Table 1. Mean values of parameters of crop performance, soil properties, water problems, crop and pest management, and pest intensity in farmers' fields at rainfed lowland sites in northeast Thailand and Vietnam. Data are from plots that received pest control according to farmers' practice. 1992.

Variable ^b		Site ^a							
		Thailand				Vietnam			
		KKN	PMI	SKN	UBN	BL	CM	LA	ST
Crop performance	YIELD	2.9	2.8	3.0	3.3	3.4	5.3	5.3	2.5
	GDURAT	147.0	163.4	166.6	158.4	106.5	139.3	98.5	117.7
	LAID	167.1	137.5	167.2	243.0	276.5	444.1	459.6	200.9
	PAN	138.6	138.3	141.6	150.5	354.2	452.1	522.9	408.3
	PHGHT	130.4	136.3	136.4	146.6	90.8	109.9	92.8	83.1
Soil properties	SAND	43.9	42.4	67.3	67.9	2.5	5.8	5.8	4.7
	SILT	21.4	20.4	20.7	25.1	42.2	41.0	44.4	42.3
	CLAY	35.1	37.4	12.1	7.3	55.2	53.2	49.8	53.0
	CARBON	.8	.8	.4	.6	1.3	1.9	2.1	1.1
	TLAYER	9.6	11.8	11.2	12.6	15.5	16.0	16.5	15.0
	PH	5.0	5.2	4.9	4.4	5.3	4.6	4.5	4.9
	CEC	4.4	11.4	4.1	4.6	8.9	11.9	12.8	10.8
	P	.3	2.0	1.1	2.0	2.0	4.3	4.8	1.5
	K	.4	.7	.2	.2	.3	.4	.2	.2
Water problems	SDROUGHT	.0	.4	.0	.0	1.0	.8	.3	1.0
	VDROUGHT	.0	.2	.0	.0	.8	.3	.0	1.0
	VFLOOD	.0	.0	.0	.0	.0	.0	.0	.3
	GDROUGHT	.2	.2	.0	.0	.0	.0	.3	.0
Crop and pest management	NAPP	20.2	31.2	11.6	22.0	170.4	124.2	103.0	76.0
	NOHAPP	.0	.0	.0	.0	1.8	1.5	1.3	.0
	NOPEST	.2	.0	.6	.8	6.0	5.0	3.5	.0
	NOHWEED	.6	.6	1.2	.6	.3	.3	1.8	1.0
		RD6	LPT123 KDML 105	RD6	KDML 105	IR13240	IR42	IR50404 IR9729	IR64
Pest intensity	BS	.0	.2	.0	.0	3.9	3.4	2.5	4.9
	DF	.0	.2	.0	.1	2.9	2.0	.1	1.3
	DH	.1	.0	.0	.0	2.9	1.3	1.3	.6
	DP	2.4	10.4	1.5	.8	26.5	15.0	23.6	38.7
	LF	.0	.0	.1	.0	.8	11.0	1.2	.8
	LS	.0	.0	.0	.0	8.6	4.5	.4	1.8
	MC_SBED	.0	.0	.0	.0	.0	.0	5.5	.0
	OTD	.4	.0	.0	.0	4.1	7.2	4.8	12.4
	PB	.0	.0	.0	.0	.1	.1	2.0	2.9
	R	.0	.6	.0	.0	.4	3.9	1.5	1.0
	RR	.0	.0	.0	.0	14.0	70.0	4.4	.0
	RS	.0	.0	.0	.0	1.3	.2	8.2	.3
	SHB	.3	.0	.0	1.4	.5	5.5	1.8	.0
	SHR	.0	.0	.1	.0	2.9	2.3	1.9	2.0
	SIDL	.0	.0	.0	.0	.5	.6	3.5	.2
	SIDS	.0	.0	.0	.0	4.2	.1	.0	.0
	SIDP	.0	.0	.0	.0	68.3	76.7	71.3	31.9
	TH_SBED	.0	.0	.0	.0	40.8	3.3	2.5	.0
	WCOVER	3.4	4.1	11.6	4.8	19.6	20.0	9.0	5.0
	WH	3.2	.0	.0	1.5	5.2	.5	2.7	1.5

^aSite names: KKN = Khon Kaen, PMI = Phi Mai, SKN = Sakhon Nakhon, UBN = Ubon; BL = Bac Lieu, CM = Ca Mau, LA = Long An, ST = Soc Trang; soil properties: SAND, SILT, CLAY CARBON = % sand, silt, clay, soil C respectively, TLAYER = depth of top layer in cm, PH = soil pH (in H₂O), CEC = cation exchange capacity (meq/100 g soil), P = ppm P, K = meq K/100 g soil; water problems: S/V/GDROUGHT (FLOOD) = seedling-/vegetative-/generative phase drought stress (or submergence), respectively, 0 = none, 1 = observed in all cases crop and pest management: NAPP = kg N applied/ha, NOHAPP, NOPEST = no. herbicide- any kind of pesticide applications, NOHWEED = no. hand weedings, VARIETY = prevailing varieties; crop performance: YIELD = measured plot yield in t/ha, GDURAT = growth duration in days; LAID = area under the leaf area index curve (m²/m²-d), PAN = final no. panicles/m², PHGHT = maximum plant height in cm; pest intensity: mean % severity/day: BS = brown spot, DF= other defoliation. DH = stem borer deadhearts, DP = dirty panicle, LF= leaf folder damage, LS = leaf scald, MC_SBED = mole cricket damage in seed bed, OTD = other tiller damage, PB = panicle blast, R = rat damage, RR = root rot at maximum leaf area stage RS = red stripe disease, SHB = sheath blight, SHR = sheath rot, SIDL = sucking insect damage on leaves, SIDS = sucking insect damage on sheaths, SIDP = sucking insect damage on panicles, TH_SBED = thrips damage in seed bed, WCOVER = weed cover (%/d); maximum % severity: FS_m = false smut, WH = stem borer whiteheads; only pest problems exceeding 2.5% intensity at one site at least are presented; no. fields/site: 4-5.

Table 2. Correlation coefficients of relationships among parameters of crop performance, soil properties, crop and pest management, and pest intensity measured in farmers' fields at rainfed lowland sites in Vietnam and northeast Thailand. Data are pooled across plots that received different intensities of pest control.^a 1992.

	YIELD	NAPP	NOWEED ^b	NOPEST	VDIS	VDISINS	GDISINS	VGDISINS	WCOVER
CLAY	.35	.59**	.12	.47*	.72**	.73**	.57**	.69**	.27
SILT	.51**	.65**	.25	.64**	.67**	.72**	.68**	.66**	.35
SAND	-.45*	-.67**	-.19	-.59**	-.77**	-.79**	-.66**	-.74**	-.33
TLAYER	.58**	.59**	.13	.57**	.70**	.71**	.44*	.58**	.22
CARBON	.75**	.60**	.29	.61**	.72**	.75**	.61**	.71**	.35
PH	-.37**	.15	-.24*	-.04	-.10	-.14	.08	.03	-.01
CEC	.48**	.41**	.10	.17	.62**	.63**	.52**	.64**	.20
P	.56**	.40**	.39**	.28*	.49**	.54**	.18	.34**	.23
K	-.00	.02	-.14	-.08	-.18	-.17	-.09	-.01	-.02
NAPP	.45*		.32	.74**	.61**	.68**	.63**	.66**	.56**
NOWEED	.32	.32		.44*	.36	.41*	.29	.36	.49*
NOPEST	.63**	.74**	.44*		.62**	.66**	.51**	.56**	.48*
AYIELD	.67**	.76**	.33	.81**	.77**	.81**	.67**	.76**	.56**
VDIS	.51**	.61**	.36	.62**		.98**	.59**	.82**	.42*
VDISINS	.53**	.68**	.41*	.66**	.98**		.60**	.83**	.52**
GDISINS	.31	.63**	.29	.51**	.59**	.60**		.90**	.27
VGDISINS	.40*	.66**	.36	.56**	.82**	.83**	.90**		.39*
WCOVER	.30	.56**	.49*	.48*	.42*	.52**	.27	.39*	

^aVDIS = % total disease on vegetative plant parts; VDISINS = % total disease and insect damage on vegetative plant parts; GDISINS = % total disease and insect damage on generative plant parts and on whole tillers; VGDISINS = VDISINS + GDISINS; for definition of other parameters. see Table 1; one-tailed test, n = 93; * = significant at p = 0.01; ** = significant at p = 0.001; correlation coefficients were truncated; pest control treatments: a) no control, b) control according to farmers' practices, c) pest control 4-5 times during growing season.

^bNOWEED = number of weed control measures (hand weeding and/or herbicide application).

vegetative phase at some sites in Vietnam.

A wide spectrum of disease and insect damage was observed. Severity ratings of biotic constraints were generally higher at sites in Vietnam than at those in Thailand. High severity ratings of dirty panicles and weed infestation were observed in both countries. Noticeable levels of leaf scald, brown spot, red stripe, root rot, sheath blight, leaf folder damage, whitehead damage, and discoloration due to sucking insects (especially on panicles), tiller damage caused by rats and other pests, and seedbed damage due

to thrips and/or mole crickets were observed, mainly in Vietnam.

Correlation analyses showed a complex structure of intercorrelations among parameters of crop performance, soil fertility and water-holding capacity, crop and pest management intensity, and pest intensity (Table 2). High actual yields of sites, high physiological potential production levels as determined by parameters of soil fertility and water-holding capacity, high fertilizer and pest control inputs, and high pest intensities were closely associated.

Pest intensity may primarily depend

on the physiological potential production level and not on the intensity of pest control while the willingness of farmers to invest in pest control may mainly depend on a site's yield potential. In this light, cause-effect relationships between site-specific conditions and pest problems and the profitability of pest control need to be critically examined. The data can be useful for characterizing patterns of and interrelations among cropping and pest control practices, factors determining productivity level, and pest problems in rainfed lowland rice areas. ■

Integrated pest management—diseases

Efficacy of three fungicides for controlling growth of five seedborne fungi associated with rice grain spotting

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Many fungi may cause rice grain spotting. The presence of fungi and discoloration reduce rice seed quality. Fungi may appear externally on the lemma and palea and/or internally in the grain. Grains with black dots, pigmentation, chalkiness, and stains from the Province of Corrientes, Argentina, were studied. We isolated 10 fungi from field-infected panicles using the blotter test method, following the rules of the International

Seed Testing Association. The following were selected for an in vitro control test due to their importance and frequency: *Bipolaris oryzae*, *Curvularia lunata*, an unidentified species, and *Fusarium semitectum*. *Fusarium moniliforme* was included as an ordinary pathogenic control species.

We used fungicides thiabendazole, carbendazim, and mancozeb. Solutions were prepared using 50, 100, 500, and